

APPENDIX 1: Primary textual references to ‘Lamri’

TOPONYM	SOURCE & REFERENCE	DATE	GEOGRAPHY	MATERIAL CULTURE REFERENCES
<p>Pu-luo (P’u-lo)</p> <p>Po-luo-(suo) (P’o-lo-[so])</p> <p>(Chinese)</p>	<p><i>Kālodaka’s Sutra of the Twelve Stages</i> / Jia Dan (Chia Tan)</p> <p>O.W. Wolters, <i>Early Indonesian Commerce: A Study of the Origins of Śrīvijaya</i> (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1967), 178-196.</p>	<p>392 / c. 800</p>	<p>Chinese records of this toponym may “represent a continuous string of notices to another center in northern Sumatra.”</p> <p>“the main port which served the northern region of Sumatra, known to the Arabs as <i>Rāmnī</i>, and it had considerable antiquity.”</p> <p>“In later times... as a result of trading with Indian Moslems, became a famous commercial centre”</p>	<p>“42 kinds of perfumes and white glass,” camphor</p>
<p>al-Rāmanī (Arabic)</p>	<p><i>Akhbār al-ṣīn wa’l-hind</i>, Book I</p> <p>A new Arabic edition, English translation and introduction to this text by Tim Mackintosh-Smith can be found in: Philip F. Kennedy and Shawkat M. Toorawa, <i>Two Arabic Travel Books</i> (New York: New York University Press, 2014), 24-27.</p>	<p>851/2</p>	<p>Book I describes a large island measuring 800-900 <i>farsakhs</i> (approximately 5,000 km) long that was reportedly “ruled by several kings”</p> <p>“The island faces two seas, those of Harkand and Salāhiṭ.”</p>	<p>“It has places where gold is mined and, in an areas known as Faṣūr, sources from which the high-grade sort of camphor comes.”</p> <p>“there are many elephants, and also sapan wood and rattans.”</p>

al-Rāmanī (Arabic)	<i>Akhbār al-ṣīn wa'l-hind</i> , Book II <i>Two Arabic Travel Books</i> , 88/89.	884	Book II identifies al-Rāmanī as measuring 800 <i>farsakhs</i> and included among the realms of the Maharaja of al-Zābaj.	“home to the places where sapan wood, camphor, and other such trees grow.”
Rāmī (Arabic)	Ibn Khurdādhbih G.R. Tibbetts, <i>A Study of the Arabic Texts Containing Material on South-East Asia</i> (Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1979), 27-28.	c. 850	Located beyond Sirandīb	Rhinoceros, buffaloes without tails, bamboo, brazil-wood
Rāmnī (Arabic)	Ibn al-Faḡīh (d. 903) Tibbetts, <i>Arabic Texts</i> , 30.	c. 900	Echo of the information presented in the <i>Akhbār al-ṣīn wa'l-hind</i> and Ibn Khurdādhbih	“The people are vigorous and they hunt the elephant... Some of its kings possess exquisite scents such as sandal and mace, but no one is allowed them except the kin in question.”
Rāmī (Arabic)	Abū Zayd Tibbetts, <i>Arabic Texts</i> , 33.	916	Echo of the information presented in the <i>Akhbār al-ṣīn wa'l-hind</i>	Echo of the information presented in the <i>Akhbār al-ṣīn wa'l-hind</i>
Rāmīn (Arabic)	Mas'ūdī, <i>Murūj al-Dhahab</i> Tibbetts, <i>Arabic Texts</i> , 36.	943	A thousand <i>parasangs</i> in distance from Sirandīb; "well populated, governed by kings." Later he says that Rāmnī belongs to the Mahārāja.	“They are full of gold mines, and nearby is the land of Faṣūr, whence is derived the <i>faṣūrī</i> camphor, which is only found there in the years that have many storms and earthquakes.”
Lāmūrī (Arabic)	<i>‘Ajā’ib al-hind</i> G.S.P. Freeman-Grenville, <i>Captain Buzurg ibn Shahriyar of Ram</i>	953	Ships towed by its anchor chains by a giant lobster off the coast of Lāmūrī...	“On the coast of Sanfin, in the Lamuri and Qaqualla valleys, there live monkeys of extraordinary size...”

	<i>Hurmuz. The book of the wonders of India, mainland, sea and islands</i> (London: East-West Publications, 1980), 5-6; 40-41.			<p>“It was said that some shipwrecked sailors forced to go from the neighborhood of Faṅṣūr to Lāmūrī, refrained from marching at night for fear of these <i>zarāfa</i>...”</p> <p>“also on these islands and enormous quantity of ants, especially on Lamuri Island, where they are enormous.”</p>
Ilamuridesam (Tamil)	<p>Thanjavur inscription</p> <p>Vijay Sakhuja & Sangeeta Sakhuja, “Rajendra Chola I’s Naval Expedition to Southeast Asia: A Nautical Perspective,” in: Hermann Kulke, K. Kesavapany, & Vijay Sakhuja, Eds. <i>Nagapattinam to Suvarnadwipa: Reflections on the Chola Naval Expeditions to Southeast Asia</i> (Singapore: ISEAS Press, 2009), 78.</p>	1025	Listed among the places attacked by Chola Naval expeditions.	“Ilamuridesam whose fierce strength rose in war”
Lambrē / Lamrin (Armenian)	Kéram Kévonian, "Un itinéraire arménien de la mer de Chine," in <i>Histoire de Barus. Le Site de Lobu Tua. I. Etudes et Documents</i> , ed. C. Guillot (Paris: Cahiers d'Archipel 30, 1998), pp. 54-66	1112	Described not just as one port, but also the name applied to a longer stretch of the coast of northern Sumatra	
Lan-li (Chinese)	Zhou Qufei, 1178. <i>Lingwai Daida</i> (Representative Answers from the Region beyond the Mountains).	1178	Set sail with north wind after the mid-winter from <i>Guangdong</i> . About forty	sappanwood, white tin and long white rattan

	Reprinted and annotated by Yang Wuquan, Beijing: Zhonghua Publishing, 1999, p. 90.		days arrived in a place called <i>Lan-li</i> . Stay until next winter (year), set sail again with northeast wind and only reach (the destination of Oman) in sixty days with tail wind.	
Lan-wu-li (Chinese)	Zhao Rugua's <i>Zhu Fan Zhi</i> Friedrich Hirth & W.W. Rockhill, <i>Chau Ju-Kua: His Work on the Chinese and Arab Trade in the twelfth and thirteenth Centuries, entitled Chu-Fan-Chi</i> (St. Petersburg: Imperial Academy of Sciences, 1911), 72.	1225	80 days sail from Quanzhou. A further 20 or so days to Sri Lanka (Xi-lan) with a north wind.	sappan wood, elephant tusks, white rattan
Lan-li (Chinese)	<i>Song Shi</i> (Song Dynasty History, 1343), juan 490. Reprinted, Beijing: Zhonghua Publishing, 1977, p. 14121.	1343	Ship sails (from Quanzhou) for forty days to Lan-li. Set sail the next year for another sixty odd days to reach the Arab country.	
Lambri (Franco-Italian)	Marco Polo's <i>Le Devisement du monde</i> <i>The Travels of Marco Polo: The Complete Yule-Cordier Edition - Including the unabridged third edition (1903) of Henry Yule's annotated translation, as revised by Henri Cordier, together with</i>	1298	"In the time of the Sung Dynasty ships from Zayton bound for <i>Tashi</i> , or Arabia, used to sail in forty days to a place called <i>Lanli-poi</i> ... There they passed the winter... sailing again when the wind became fair, they	An entrepôt for camphor and "all sorts of spices... There are also plenty of unicorns in that country, and abundance of game in birds and beasts"

	<i>Cordier's later volume of notes and addenda (1920), 2 vols. (New York: Dover Publications, 1993), II: 299-301</i>		reached Arabia in sixty days.”	
Lāmūrī (Arabic)	Rashīd al-Dīn (d. 1318) Tibbetts, <i>Arabic Texts</i> , 60-61	c. 1300	“The island of Lāmūrī is very large and is beyond Ceylon. It has its own king. Beyond it is found the island of Sūmūtra.”	“Opposite Lāmūrī is the island of Nākavāram which produces red ambergris... They are subject to the Emperor of China.”
Lamori (Latin/ Italian)	Friar Odoric de Pordenone Henry Yule, <i>Cathay and the Way Thither: Being a Collection of Medieval Notices of China</i> (London: Hakluyt Society, 1913), II: 146-150.	1316- 1330	In this country the north star ceases to be visible. Inhabitants go naked, holding land and spouses in common, and practicing cannibalism. To the south is Sumoltra, whose people are at war with the ‘naked’ people of Lamori.	gold, lign-aloes, camphor
Nan-Wu-Li (Chinese)	Wang Dayuan’s <i>Daoyi Zhilue</i> W.W. Rockhill, “Notes on the Relations and Trade of China with the Eastern Archipelago and the Coast of the Indian Ocean during the Fourteenth Century, Part II,”	1349	“Great mountainlike waves dash against it” The natives live all over the hills, each family in its own house. Both men and women do up their hair in a	The soil is poor, the crops sparse, the climate hot. The native products are helmeted hornbill casque, shells of turtles and tortoise-shell. Its laka-wood is superior to any other in aroma. The goods used (by the Chinese) in

	<i>T'oung Pao</i> , second series 16.1 (March 1915): 148-149.		knot and leave the upper part of their bodies bare, wrapping a piece of cloth around them as a sarong.	trading here are gold, silver, iron-ware, rose-water, red <i>si bu</i> (絲布 'silk cloth'), camphor, porcelain-ware with designs in blue and white, and such like things.
Lamuri (Javanese)	<i>Deśawarṇana (Nāgarakṛtāgama)</i> , translated by Stuart Robson (Leiden: KITLV Press), 13-2-1/ p. 33.	1365	Listed among the Sumatran tributaries of Majapahit: "All these countries are subject and obedient"	
Nan-wu-li/ Nan-bo-li (Chinese)	<i>Ming Shi-Lu</i> Geoff Wade, <i>Southeast Asia in the Ming-Shi-Lu</i> : http://www.epress.nus.edu.sg/msl/search/node/Nan-wu-li	1405-1423	14 mentions of Nan-bo-li, and 6 of Nan-wu-li, mostly on the dispatch of emissaries and the arrival of tribute delegations to the Chinese court.	
Nan-bo-li (Nan-po-li) (Chinese)	Ma Huan, <i>Ying-Yai Sheng-Lan: The Overall Survey of the Ocean's Shores</i> , Translated from the Chinese text edited by Feng Ch'eng-Chün with introduction, notes, and appendices by J. V. G. Mills (Cambridge University Press – Published for the Hakluyt Society, 1970), 122-124.	1433	Three days and nights sail (with a fair wind) west from Su-men-da-la (Pasai). "The population comprises only something over a thousand families. All are Muslims... On the east, the territory adjoins the boundary of the king of Li-tai [Li-dai]; on both west and north it abuts on the great sea; if you go south, there are mountains; [and south of	High-quality ('lotus-flower') laka-wood and rhinoceros, large coral 'trees' "Fish and shrimps are very cheap. Rice and grain are scarce." Tribute brought to the Imperial Court by the King, who accompanied the treasure ships of Zheng He.

			<p>the mountains there is the great sea again.”</p> <p>“In the sea to the north-west of the country, there is a large, flat-topped steep mountain, which can be reached in half a day; its name is Mao mountain. On the west of this mountain, too, it is all great sea; indeed, this is the Western Ocean, [this area being] named the Na-Mo-Li ocean. Ships coming from the west all take in sail [here]”</p>	
al-Rāmanī (Arabic)	<p>Aḥmad b. Mājid al-Najdī, <i>Kitāb al-Fawā'id fī uṣūl al-baḥr wa 'l-qawā'id</i>.</p> <p>G.R. Tibbetts, <i>Arab Navigation in the Indian Ocean Before the Coming of the Portuguese</i> (London: Luzac & Co., 1971), 493.</p>	1490	"On the coast here the text first places <i>Lāmūrī</i> (...) which is the port in the neighbourhood of Aceh.”	
Lāmūrī (Arabic)	<p>Sulaymān al-Mahrī's <i>al-'Umda al-mahriyya fī ḍabṭ al-'ilm -al-baḥriyya</i></p> <p>Gabriel Ferrand, “L'empire sumatranais de Çrīvijaya,” <i>Journal Asiatique</i> 20 (1922): 102.</p>	1511	The nearby pepper port of Pedir is located “under the Lāmūrī mountain.”	

Lambry (Portuguese)	Tomé Pires, <i>Suma Oriental</i> Armando Cortesão (Tr.) <i>The Suma Oriental of Tomé Pires: An account of the East from the Red Sea to Japan, Written in Malacca and India in 1512-1515</i> . 2 vols. (London: Hakluyt Society, 1944), I: 137-138)	1512-15	“Achin is the first country on the channel side of the island and <i>Lambry</i> is right next to it, and stretches inland.”	Just a few years later, in 1518, another Portuguese chronicler neglects any mention of Lamri in his account of the northern coast of Sumatra. Mansel Longworth Dames (Trans./Ed.) <i>The Book of Duarte Barbosa: An Account of the Countries Bordering on the Indian Ocean and their Inhabitants, Written by Duarte Barbosa, and Completed about the Year 1518 A.D.</i> (London: Hakluyt Soceity, 1921), II: 181-189.
Nan-Po-Li (Chinese)	Huang Shêng ts'êng's <i>Hsi yang chao kung tien lu</i> W.W. Rockhill, “Notes on the Relations and Trade of China with the Eastern Archipelago and the Coast of the Indian Ocean during the Fourteenth Century, Part II,” <i>T'oung Pao</i> , second series 16.1 (March 1915): 79	1520	Repetition of information on the port from earlier Chinese texts.	
Lamiri (Malay)	<i>Sejarah Melayu</i> (MS Raffles 18) Transcribed by Abdul Rahman Haji Ismail in: Cheah Boon Kheng, Ed., <i>Sejarah Melayu: The Malay Annals</i> (Kuala Lumpur: Malaysian Branch	c. 1530	Lamiri located between Fansur and Aru on the itinerary of Nakhoda Ismail in a conversion narrative of al-Malik al-Şāliḥ of Pasai (d. 1297).	The text claims that the inhabitants of Lamiri also embraced Islam at that time.

	of the Royal Asiatic Society, 2009), 107.			
Lambrij (Portuguese)	loão de Barros, <i>Decadas da Asia Decada terceira da Asia de loão de Barros: Dos feitos qve os Portvgveses fezerão no descobrimento & conquista dos mares & terras do Oriente</i> (Lisboa: lorge Rodgriguez, 1628), 114v.	1536-63	Lambrij mentioned among a number of other small port polities that were incorporated into the expanding sultanate of Aceh.	
Lamri (Malay)	<i>Hikayat Aceh</i> Teuku Iskandar (Ed.), <i>De Hikajat Atjéh</i> ('s-Gravenhage: Nijhoff, 1958), 69-73.	c. 1610	<i>Negeri Lamri</i> features in this later narrative source as one of a number of smaller polities on the coast of northern Sumatra.	Raja Muzaffar Shah of Lamri supplies cannon captured from the Portuguese to aid Makota Alam against its neighbor Dar al-Kamal in struggle leading to the establishment of the Sultanate of Aceh around the turn of the 16th century.

Appendix 2. Ceramics recovered from cutting back the Lamreh Beach Section.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Minnan					4						
China	Fujian	Minnan		1									
India										1			
India							4						
India												5	
Unknown												2	
Total Count				1			8			1		7	17

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1003. The datable sherds range from 1200 – 1400 C. E., with the latest date starting in 1250. Two AMS dates from animal bone samples from this unit date 1200 – 1270 and 1210 – 1280 C.E. (cal). It is likely that all ceramics in this unit date to the 13th century.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Cizao									1		
China	Fujian	Minnan		13									
China	Fujian	Minnan					12						
China	Fujian	Minnan	2										
China	Guangdong						14						
India										7			
India								24					
India												100	
Unknown							4						
Unknown												12	
Total			2	13			30	24		7	1	112	189

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1008. The datable sherds range from 1200 – 1400 C. E., with the latest date starting in 1280. Two AMS dates from animal bone and tooth samples from this unit date 1220 – 1300, and 1260 – 1310/1360 – 1390 C.E. (cal). It is likely that ceramics in this unit date to the late 13th century through mid to late 14th century.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Minnan					1						
China	Quangdong						1						
China	Zhejiang	Longquan							1				
China	Zhejiang	Longquan		1									
India						1							
India								6					
India												3	
Total				1		1	2	6	1			3	14

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1009. The datable sherds range from 1200 – 1400 C. E.. Two AMS dates from animal bone and charcoal samples from this unit date 1300 – 1430, and 1260 – 1310/1360 – 1390 C.E. (cal). It is likely that ceramics in this unit date from the late 13th century through mid to late 14th century.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Minnan					1						
China	Guangdong						1						
China	Zhejiang	Longquan		1									
China							1						
India						2							
India							1						
India				1									
India												12	
Persia												1	
Total				2		2	4					13	21

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1020. The datable sherds mostly range from 1200 – 1400 C. E. This unit contained two early sherds – a blue glazed sherd from Persia that we believe dates between 900 – 1100, and a sherd of Indian northern grey ware that possibly dates to the first two centuries of the first millennium C.E. This unit is a debris flow from up slope. While both of these sherds are residual, they provide evidence that there was some activity at Lamreh prior to the main phase of occupation that started in the 13th century.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China							1						
India												5	
Indonesia					1								
Total					1		1					5	7

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1023. The datable sherds range from 1200 – 1400 C. E. An AMS date from animal bone from this unit date 1280 - 1410 C.E. (cal).

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Minnan		1									
China	Fujian	Minnan					2						
China	Guangdong						8						
India								5					
India				2									
India												22	
Total				3			10	5				22	40

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1024. The datable sherds mostly range from 1200 – 1400 C. E. This unit contained two sherds of Indian northern grey ware that possibly dates to the first two centuries of the first millennium C.E. While both of these sherds are residual, they provide evidence that there was some activity at Lamreh prior to the main phase of occupation that started in the 13th century.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
India												4	
Total												4	4

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1026. The datable sherds possibly range from 1200 – 1400 C. E.

Country	Region	Sub-Region	Basin	Bowl	Crucible	Globular Vessel	Jar	Khadai	Plate	Pot	Vase	Unknown	Total
China	Fujian	Minnan		13									
China	Fujian	Minnan					6						
China	Guangdong						10						
China	Southern China						11						
China	Zhejiang	Longquan		2									
India						11							
India								7					
India										5			
India												54	
Unknown						3							
Unknown							1						
Unknown												17	
Total				15		14	28	7		5		71	140

Ceramics from Lamreh Beach Section Unit 1027. This unit is the tsunami deposit. It contains a large amount of ceramic material, that mainly dates from 1200 – 1400 C. E. An AMS date from animal tooth from this unit date 1270 – 1310/1360 - 1390 C.E. (cal).

Appendix 4 - Inventory of Sites located in Lamreh Village

Site	Coordinates	Grave Stones Count	Grave Types	Sherd Count	Ceramic Date Range	Ceramic Source
1	N: 05° 36' 30.7" E: 095° 32' 07.2"	18	9 (Type 6) 3 (Type 7) 6 (Unknown)	28	Date Range 1150 - 1550 Main period of activity 1400- 1500	Indonesia 25% Burma 25% China 17% Thailand 14% Unknown 14% Vietnam 3%
2	N: 05° 36' 28.4" E: 095° 31' 48.7"	7	3 (Type 1) 1 (Type 4) 3 (Type 7)	93	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300-1400. 4 Sherds of imperial Longquan ware dating between 1400 - 1450.	China 38% Indonesia 26% Burma 16% Thailand 7% Unknown 10%
3	N: 05° 36' 24.2" E: 095° 31' 49.1"	1	1 (Type 7)	54	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300-1400; 1450-1550	China 40% Indonesia 38% Burma 12% Thailand 3% Unknown 3%
4	N: 05° 36' 24.3" E: 095° 31' 49.7"	2	1 (Type 4) 1 (Unknown)	4	Date Range 1200 - 1400 Main period of activity 1300-1400	China 75% Unknown 25%
5	N: 05° 36' 29.97" E: 095° 31' 49.55"	4	4 (Type 6)		No Ceramics	No ceramics
6	N: 05° 36' 23.94" E: 095° 31' 47.82"	1	1 (Unknown)		No Ceramics	No ceramics
7	N: 05° 36' 21.43" E: 095° 31' 46.34"	3	No Graves	1	Date Range 1450 - 1550 Main period of activity 1450-1550	Burma 100%
8	N: 05° 36' 32.93" E: 095° 31' 48.84"	3	1 (Type 6) 1 (Type Other) 1 (Unknown)	207	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1200-1400; 1450-1550	Indonesia 43% China 41% Burma 7% Thailand 3% Unknown 4%
9	N: 05° 36' 35.36" E: 095° 31' 48.67"		No Graves	156	Date Range 1100 - 1530 Main period of activity 1200-1500	Indonesia 51% China 25% Burma 7% Thailand 1% Unknown 14%
10	N: 05° 36' 39.6" E: 095° 31' 47.7"	19	1 (Type 6) 18 (Type 7)	56	Date Range 1200 - 1530 Main period of activity 1200-1400	Indonesia 44% China 42% Burma 3% Thailand 1% Unknown 8%
11	N: 05° 36' 40.3" E: 095° 31' 47.1"	1	1 (Type 5)	12	Date Range 1200 - 1400 Main period of activity 1200-1350	China 58% Indonesia 41%

12	N: 05° 36' 41.7" E: 095° 31' 46.2"	0	No Graves	92	Date Range 1200 - 1530 Main period of activity 1350-1400	Indonesia 51% China 24% Burma 20% Unknown 2%
13	N: 05° 36' 37.8" E: 095° 31' 49.1"	1	1 (Type 6)	27	Date Range 1200 - 1600 Main period of activity 1200-1350	Indonesia 48% China 37% Burma 11% Thailand 3%
14	N: 05° 36' 40.74" E: 095° 31' 50.84"	4	1 (Type 1) 1 (Type 4) 2 (Unknown)	15	Date Range 1200 - 1521 Main period of activity 1250-1350	China 67% Indonesia 20% Burma 6% Thailand 6%
15	N: 05° 36' 43.4" E: 095° 31' 46"	5	2 (Type 3) 1 (Type 7) 2 (Unknown)	13	Date Range 1200 - 1530 Main period of activity 1400 - 1500	Thailand 23% China 19% Indonesia 15% Burma 15%
16	N: 05° 36' 47.9" E: 095° 31' 48.1"	6	2 (Type 2) 1 (Type 3) 1 (Type 5) 1 (Type 7) 1 (Unknown)	73	Date Range 1200 - 1510 Main period of activity 1200 - 1500	China 53% Burma 25% Indonesia 14% Thailand 8%
17	N: 05° 36' 48.84" E: 095° 31' 49.76"	4	1 (Type 1) 3 (Type 3)		No ceramics	No ceramics
18	N: 05° 36' 49.1" E: 095° 31' 51.4"	3	2 (Type 7) 1 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
19	N: 05° 36' 40.74" E: 095° 31' 50.84"	0	No Graves	40	Date Range 1200 - 1530 Main period of activity 1200 - 1300; 1400 - 1500	China 45% Indonesia 22% Burma 12% Thailand 10%
20	N: 05° 36' 46.2" E: 095° 31' 47.7"	0	No Graves	81	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1200 - 1300; 1400 - 1500	China 41% Indonesia 25% Burma 17% Thailand 4%
21	N: 05° 36' 44.5" E: 095° 31' 49.1"	2	1 (Type 4) 1 (Type 7)	122	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1200 - 1300; 1400 - 1500	China 49% Indonesia 25% Burma 10% Thailand 10% Vietnam 2% South India 1%
22	N: 05° 36' 42.23" E: 095° 31' 50.15"	0	No Graves	147	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1200 - 1350; 1400 - 1500	China 53% Indonesia 25% Thailand 7% Burma 5%

23	N: 05° 36' 44.6" E: 095° 31' 50.4"	0	No Graves	85	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1240 - 1400	China 67% Thailand 11% Indonesia 11% Burma 4% South India 2%
24	N: 05° 36' 44.0" E: 095° 31' 51.2"	5	1 (Type 3) 3 (Type 7) 1 (Other)	26	Date Range 1270 - 1450 Main period of activity 1270 - 1400	China 65% Indonesia 27% Burma 8%
25	N: 05° 36' 43.4" E: 095° 31' 53.6"	3	3 (Type 7)	78	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 73% Thailand 4% Indonesia 12% Burma 4% South India 8%
26	N: 05° 36' 42.71" E: 095° 31' 54.14"	4	1 (Type 1) 1 (Type 4) 2 (6)	101	Date Range 1250 - 1500 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 73% Thailand 6% Burma 5% Indonesia 4% South India 2% Vietnam 2%
27	N: 05° 36' 45.2" E: 095° 31' 51.6"	0	No Graves	103	Date Range 1300 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400; 1450 - 1550	China 56% Indonesia 28% South India 6% Thailand 6% Burma 2% Vietnam 1%
28	N: 05° 36' 41.50" E: 095° 31' 52.20"	0	No Graves	221	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 75% Indonesia 14% Thailand 6% Burma 2% Vietnam 2%
29	N: 05° 36' 41.6" E: 095° 31' 53.5"	0	No Graves	151	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1500	China 79% Indonesia 9% Burma 5% Thailand 4% Vietnam 3%
30	N: 05° 36' 41.5" E: 095° 31' 54.6"	4	1 (Type 2) 1 (Type 7) 2 (Unknown)	397	Date Range 1300 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400; 1450 - 1550	China 65% Indonesia 17% South India 2% Burma 1% Thailand < 1% Vietnam < 1%
31	N: 05° 36' 36.46" E: 095° 32' 00.11"	1	1 (Type 7)	128	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1500	China 67% Indonesia 36% Thailand 9% Vietnam 2% Burma < 1%

32	N: 05° 36' 38.1" E: 095° 31' 59.4"	4	4 (Unknown)	28	Date Range 1200 - 1700 Main period of activity 1250 - 1350	China 54% Indonesia 25% Thailand 7% Burma 7%
33	N: 05° 36' 39.9" E: 095° 32' 00.7"	10	2 (Type 1) 1 (Type 4) 3 (Type 6) 2 (Type 7) 2 (Unknown)	9	Date Range 1200 - 1350 Main period of activity 1200 - 1300	China 33% Indonesia 33%
34	N: 05° 36' 38.5" E: 095° 32' 01.8"	2	2 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
35	N: 05° 36' 39.49" E: 095° 31' 56.78"	0	No Graves	69	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1200 - 1400	China 54% Indonesia 26% Thailand 8% Burma 4%
36	N: 05° 36' 38.10" E: 095° 31' 57.49"	0	No Graves	183	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1200 - 1400	China 51% Indonesia 37% Thailand 5% Burma 1%
37	N: 05° 36' 36.0" E: 095° 31' 58.35"	1	1 (Type 7)	117	Date Range 1200 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 56% Indonesia 29% Thailand 4% Burma 3% South India < 1%
38	N: 05° 36' 37.2" E: 095° 31' 54.5"	0	No Graves	438	Date Range 1100 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1500	China 55% Indonesia 26% Thailand 6% Burma 5% South India < 1% Syria/Raqqa < 1% Vietnam < 1%
39	N: 05° 36' 36.6" E: 095° 31' 55.3"	8	3 (Type 3) 2 (Type 4) 3 (Type 7)	7	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1500	China 57% Indonesia 14% Thailand 14% Burma 14%
40	N: 05° 36' 30.1" E: 095° 31' 57.6"	3	3 (Type 7)	7	Date Range 1250 - 1500 Main period of activity 1250 - 1500	China 33% Burma 33% Indonesia 17%
41	N: 05° 36' 30.3" E: 095° 31' 56.9"	7	2 (Type 4) 5 (Type 7)	11	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 45% Indonesia 27% Thailand 18%
42	N: 05° 36' 31.2" E: 095° 31' 57.3"	4	4 (Type 7)	18	Date Range 1200 - 1500 Main period of activity 1300 - 1500	China 50% Burma 39% Thailand 6% Vietnam 6%

43	N: 05° 36' 32.33" E: 095° 31' 57.81"	1	1 (Type 7)	21	Date Range 1300 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	Vietnam 9% Thailand 5%
44	N: 05° 36' 29.60" E: 095° 32' 00.70"	2	2 (Type 6)	125	Date Range 1200 - 1750 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 49% Indonesia 30% Burma 11% Thailand 8% South India < 1%
45	N: 05° 36' 28.86" E: 095° 31' 57.72"	6	1 (Type 3) 1 (Type 7) 1 (Other) 3 (Unknown)	4	Date Range 1300 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 50% Indonesia 25% Burma 25%
46	N: 05° 36' 35.8" E: 095° 31' 55.3"	12	9 (Type 7) 3 (Unknown)	8	Date Range 1250 - 1400 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 88% Indonesia 12%
47	N: 05° 36' 32.89" E: 095° 31' 51.56"	2	1 (Type 2) 1 (Unknown)	3	Date Range 1250 - 1400 Main period of activity 1250 - 1350	China 100%
48	N: 05° 36' 15.0" E: 095° 31' 52.4"	16	3 (Type 1) 1 (Type 2) 3 (Type 3) 2 (Type 4) 1 (Type 7) 4 (Other) 2 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No Ceramics
49	N: 05° 36' 30.6" E: 095° 31' 52.8"	5	2 (Type 1) 1 (Type 6) 1 (Type 7) 1 (Unknown)	66	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 60% Indonesia 30% Burma 6% Thailand 1% South India 1%
50	N: 05° 36' 13.1" E: 095° 31' 01.3"	2	1 (Type 6) 1 (Type 7)		No ceramics	No ceramics
51	N: 05° 36' 17.2" E: 095° 31' 55.5"	8	1 (Type 1) 1 (Type 2) 3 (Type 3) 1 (Type 4) 2 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
52	N: 05° 36' 10.3" E: 095° 31' 59.2"	12	11 (Type 1) 1 (Type 7))		No ceramics	No ceramics
53	N: 05° 36' 15.4" E: 095° 31' 56.5"	8	1 (Type 1) 3 (Type 6) 3 (Type 7) 1 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
54	N: 05° 36' 14.4" E: 095° 31' 58.5"	2	1 (Type 1) 1 (Type 7)		No ceramics	No ceramics

55	N: 05° 36' 32.4" E: 095° 32' 04.7"	0	No Graves	91	Date Range 1200 - 1600 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 50% Indonesia 24% Thailand 11% Burma 5% South India 1%
56	N: 05° 36' 31.8" E: 095° 32' 05.61"	0	No Graves	73	Date Range 1250 - 1600 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400; 1450-1550	China 32% Indonesia 43% Thailand 10% Burma 4% South India 3% Vietnam 3%
57	N: 05° 36' 31.0" E: 095° 32' 05.9"	0	No Graves	102	Date Range 1100 - 1450 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 48% Indonesia 52% Thailand 14% South India 14%
58	N: 05° 36' 34.0" E: 095° 32' 05.5"	2	2 (Type 8)	38	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400; 1450 - 1550	China 47% Indonesia 26% Thailand 10% South India 5%
59	N: 05° 36' 34.2" E: 095° 32' 05.9"	3	1 (Type 6) 2 (Type 7)	34	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	China 56% Indonesia 21% Thailand 14% South India 9%
60	N: 05° 36' 35.59" E: 095° 32' 02.84"	6	3 (Type 1) 1 (Type 2) 2 (Type 7)		No ceramics	No ceramics
61	N: 05° 36' 34.0" E: 095° 32' 06.6"	4	1 (Type 3) 2 (Type 6) 1 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
62	N: 05° 36' 31.3" E: 095° 32' 03.1"	1	1 (Other)	96	Date Range 1200 - 1600 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400; 1450 - 1550	China 51% Indonesia 36% Thailand 8% Burma 3% South India 1%
63	N: 05° 36' 34.4" E: 095° 32' 10.2"	0	No Graves	39	Date Range 1250 - 1550 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 49% Indonesia 44% Thailand 5%
64	N: 05° 36' 33.3" E: 095° 32' 10.5"	7	3 (Type 7) 3 (Other) 1 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
65	N: 05° 36' 40.7" E: 095° 32' 02.6"	0	No Graves	9	Date Range 1300 1400 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	Indonesia 66% China 22%
66	N: 05° 36' 16.89" E: 095° 32' 32.15"	3	1 (Other) 2 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics

67	N: 05° 36' 22.7" E: 095° 32' 18.3"	6	1 (Type 1) 1 (Type 3) 2 (Type 6) 1 (Type 7) 1 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
68	N: 05° 36' 21.47" E: 095° 32' 18.97"	4	2 (Type 1) 2 (Unknown)		No ceramics	No ceramics
69	N: 05° 36' 05.14" E: 095° 32' 08.8"	0	No Graves	2	Date Range 1300 - 1500 Main period of activity 1300 - 1500	Burma 50% China 50%
70	N: 05° 36' 27.8" E: 095° 31' 40.7"	6	5 (Type 8) 1 (Other)		No ceramics	No ceramics
71	N: 05° 37' 13.4" E: 095° 35' 19.0"	0	No Graves	2	Date Range 1500 - 1600 Main period of activity 1500 - 1600	Burma 100%
72	N: 05° 37' 06.4" E: 095° 35' 10.7"	3	3 (Type 5)	3	Date Range Unkown	Indonesia 100%
73	N: 05° 37' 03.6" E: 095° 35' 10.6"	3	3 (Type 5)		No ceramics	No ceramics
74	N: 05° 36' 50.0" E: 095° 33' 29.2"	0	No Graves		No ceramics	No ceramics
75	N: 05° 36' 34.8" E: 095° 32' 18.8"	1	1 (Type 1)	13	Date Range 1300 - 1600 Main period of activity 1300 - 1400	Indonesia 31% China 15% Burma 8%
76	N: 05° 37' 31.7" E: 095° 36' 53.0"	3	2 (Type 5) 1 (Other)		No ceramics	No ceramics
77	N: 05° 36' 18.8" E: 095° 31' 47.5"	0	No Graves	16	Date Range 1250 - 1400 Main period of activity 1250 - 1400	China 75% Indonesia 25%
78	N: 05° 36' 39.6" E: 095° 32' 59.9"	0	No Graves		No ceramics	No ceramics
79	N: 05° 36' 49.15" E: 095° 32' 43.17"	0	No Graves		No ceramics	No ceramics
80	N: 05° 36' 51.1" E: 095° 32' 40.4"	0	No Graves		No ceramics	No ceramics
81	N: 05° 36' 55.3" E: 095° 32' 38.9"	0	No Graves		No ceramics	No ceramics
82	N: 05° 36' 50.6" E: 095° 35' 26.6"	1	1 (Type 5)		No ceramics	No ceramics

AB-LHR-2-GS5 S Face
18cm across 8cm thick 32cm tall
N: 05 36' 27.8" E: 095 31' 48.6"

AB-LHR-14-GS4 N Face
20cm across 13cm thick 33cm tall
N: 05 36' 40.67" E: 095 31' 50.88"

AB-LHR-49-GS4 N Face
15cm across 8cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.1" E: 095 31' 53.3"

AB-LHR-75-GS1 S Face
23cm across 13cm thick 44cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.8" E: 095 32' 18.8"

AB-LHR-2-GS7 SE Face
23cm across 10cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 27.8" E: 095 31' 48.5"

AB-LHR-33-GS1 SW Face
25cm across 8cm thick 47cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.4" E: 095 32' 01.0"

AB-LHR-54-GS1 S Face
21cm across 9cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.8" E: 095 31' 59.1"

AB-LHR-54-GS1 N Face
21cm across 9cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.8" E: 095 31' 59.1"

AB-LHR-16-GS2 SW Face
18cm across 7cm thick 42cm tall
N: 05 36' 47.6" E: 095 31' 48.0"

AB-LHR-30-GS4 S Face
13cm across 7cm thick 18cm tall
N: 05 36' 41.6" E: 095 31' 54.4"

AB-LHR-60-GS3 S Face
19cm across 9cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.51" E: 095 32' 03.08"

AB-LHR-60-GS3 W Face
19cm across 9cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.51" E: 095 32' 03.08"

AB-LHR-47-GS1
33cm across 12cm thick 98cm tall
N: 05 36' 32.92" E: 095 31' 57.53"

AB-LHR-51-GS5 S Face
18cm across 7cm thick 41cm tall
N: 05 36' 17.2" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-60-GS3 N Face
19cm across 9cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.51" E: 095 32' 03.08"

AB-LHR-60-GS3 E Face
19cm across 9cm thick 36cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.51" E: 095 32' 03.08"

AB-LHR-16-GS1 S Face
20cm across 7cm thick 47cm tall
N: 05 36' 47.6" E: 095 31' 48.1"

AB-LHR-17-GS1 S Face
23cm across 9cm thick 47cm tall
N: 05 36' 48.95" E: 095 31' 49.68"

AB-LHR-48-GS16 N Face
17cm across 7cm thick 30cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.1" E: 095 31' 52.9"

AB-LHR-39-GS2 N Face
21cm across 8cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-48-GS13 S Face
15cm across 5cm thick 26cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.2" E: 095 31' 52.8"

AB-LHR-17-GS3 S Face
22cm across 8cm thick 47cm tall
N: 05 36' 48.75" E: 095 31' 49.83"

AB-LHR-39-GS1 N Face
24cm across 9cm thick 25cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-39-GS3 S Face
12cm across 5cm thick 22cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-4-GS1 S Face
21cm across 7cm thick 62cm tall
N: 05 36' 24.3" E: 095 31' 49.6"

AB-LHR-51-GS6 S Face
15cm across 9cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 17.2" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-48-GS1 S Face
19cm across 11cm thick 31cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.1" E: 095 31' 52.3"

AB-LHR-21-GS1 E Face
17cm across 6cm thick 51cm tall
N: 05 36' 43.7" E: 095 31' 49.6"

AB-LHR-61-GS4 N Face
16cm across 7cm thick 45cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 06.3"

AB-LHR-48-GS2 S Face
20cm across 7cm thick 40cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.0" E: 095 31' 52.3"

AB-LHR-41-GS1 SE Face
23cm across 8cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.5" E: 095 31' 56.7"

AB-LHR-41-GS1 NW Face
23cm across 8cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.5" E: 095 31' 56.7"

AB-LHR-41-GS2 N Face
24cm across 9cm thick 51cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.4" E: 095 31' 56.7"

AB-LHR-41-GS2 S Face
24cm across 9cm thick 51cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.4" E: 095 31' 56.7"

AB-LHR-72-GS3 N Face
24cm across 17cm thick 35cm tall
N: 05 37' 06.0" E: 095 35' 10.2"

AB-LHR-76-GS3 E Face
20cm Dia 22cm tall
N: 05 37' 31.7" E: 095 36' 51.7"

AB-LHR-73-GS3 N Face
13cm across 7cm thick 26cm tall
N: 05 37' 03.7" E: 095 35' 10.4"

AB-LHR-82-GS1 E Face
20cm across 7cm thick 40cm tall
N: 05 36' 50.9" E: 095 35' 26.5"

AB-LHR-1-GS2 S Face
39cm across 18cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.5" E: 095 32' 07.2"

AB-LHR-1-GS12 S Face
16cm across 9cm thick 37cm tall
N: 05 36' 31.1" E: 095 32' 07.3"

AB-LHR-1-GS11 N Face
18cm across 12cm thick 67cm tall
N: 05 36' 31.1" E: 095 32' 07.3"

AB-LHR-61-GS3 S Face
20cm across 9cm thick 59cm tall
N: 05 36' 33.9" E: 095 32' 06.6"

AB-LHR-1-GS2 W Face
39cm across 18cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.5" E: 095 32' 07.2"

AB-LHR-1-GS12 W Face
16cm across 9cm thick 37cm tall
N: 05 36' 31.1" E: 095 32' 07.3"

AB-LHR-1-GS11 E Face
18cm across 12cm thick 67cm tall
N: 05 36' 31.1" E: 095 32' 07.3"

AB-LHR-61-GS3 W Face
20cm across 9cm thick 59cm tall
N: 05 36' 33.9" E: 095 32' 06.6"

AB-LHR-1-GS17 S Face
19cm across 11cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.3" E: 095 32' 06.9"

AB-LHR-1-GS17 W Face
19cm across 11cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.3" E: 095 32' 06.9"

AB-LHR-49-GS5 N Face
20cm across 12cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.7" E: 095 31' 52.6"

AB-LHR-49-GS5 E Face
20cm across 12cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.7" E: 095 31' 52.6"

AB-LHR-1-GS17 N Face
19cm across 11cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.3" E: 095 32' 06.9"

AB-LHR-1-GS17 E Face
19cm across 11cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.3" E: 095 32' 06.9"

AB-LHR-49-GS5 S Face
20cm across 12cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.7" E: 095 31' 52.6"

AB-LHR-49-GS5 W Face
20cm across 12cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 30.7" E: 095 31' 52.6"

AB-LHR-26-GS2 N Face
16cm across 9cm thick 61cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.62" E: 095 31' 54.27"

AB-LHR-26-GS2 E Face
16cm across 9cm thick 61cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.62" E: 095 31' 54.27"

AB-LHR-26-GS1 N Face
16cm across 10cm thick 72cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.72" E: 095 31' 54.22"

AB-LHR-26-GS1 E Face
16cm across 10cm thick 72cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.72" E: 095 31' 54.22"

AB-LHR-26-GS2 S Face
16cm across 9cm thick 61cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.62" E: 095 31' 54.27"

AB-LHR-26-GS2 W Face
16cm across 9cm thick 61cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.62" E: 095 31' 54.27"

AB-LHR-26-GS1 S Face
16cm across 10cm thick 72cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.72" E: 095 31' 54.22"

AB-LHR-26-GS1 W Face
16cm across 10cm thick 72cm tall
N: 05 36' 42.72" E: 095 31' 54.22"

AB-LHR-44-GS1 NW Face
28cm across 23cm thick 122cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.70" E: 095 32' 00.79"

AB-LHR-44-GS1 SW Face
28cm across 23cm thick 122cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.70" E: 095 32' 00.79"

AB-LHR-44-GS2 SE Face
24cm across 18cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.63" E: 095 32' 00.59"

AB-LHR-44-GS2 SW Face
24cm across 18cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.63" E: 095 32' 00.59"

AB-LHR-44-GS1 SE Face
28cm across 23cm thick 122cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.70" E: 095 32' 00.79"

AB-LHR-44-GS1 NE Face
28cm across 23cm thick 122cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.70" E: 095 32' 00.79"

AB-LHR-44-GS2 NE Face
24cm across 18cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.63" E: 095 32' 00.59"

AB-LHR-44-GS2 NW Face
24cm across 18cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 29.63" E: 095 32' 00.59"

AB-LHR-53-GS1 W Face
17cm across 11cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.8" E: 095 31' 56.3"

AB-LHR-53-GS1 N Face
17cm across 11cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.8" E: 095 31' 56.3"

AB-LHR-59-GS1 S Face
21cm across 10cm thick 64cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 06.2"

AB-LHR-59-GS1 W Face
21cm across 10cm thick 64cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 06.2"

AB-LHR-53-GS1 E Face
17cm across 11cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.8" E: 095 31' 56.3"

AB-LHR-53-GS1 S Face
17cm across 11cm thick 38cm tall
N: 05 36' 15.8" E: 095 31' 56.3"

AB-LHR-59-GS1 N Face
21cm across 10cm thick 64cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 06.2"

AB-LHR-59-GS1 E Face
21cm across 10cm thick 64cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 06.2"

AB-LHR-13-GS1 N Face
18cm across 10cm thick 43cm tall
N: 05 36' 37.4" E: 095 31' 49.1"

AB-LHR-13-GS1 E Face
18cm across 10cm thick 43cm tall
N: 05 36' 37.4" E: 095 31' 49.1"

AB-LHR-53-GS5 N Face
17cm across 9cm thick 60cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.9" E: 095 31' 57.6"

AB-LHR-53-GS5 E Face
17cm across 9cm thick 60cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.9" E: 095 31' 57.6"

AB-LHR-13-GS1 S Face
18cm across 10cm thick 43cm tall
N: 05 36' 37.4" E: 095 31' 49.1"

AB-LHR-13-GS1 W Face
18cm across 10cm thick 43cm tall
N: 05 36' 37.4" E: 095 31' 49.1"

AB-LHR-53-GS5 S Face
17cm across 9cm thick 60cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.9" E: 095 31' 57.6"

AB-LHR-53-GS5 W Face
17cm across 9cm thick 60cm tall
N: 05 36' 14.9" E: 095 31' 57.6"

AB-LHR-10-GS12 S Face
18cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS12 W Face
18cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS13 S Face
19cm across 16cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.6"

AB-LHR-10-GS13 W Face
19cm across 16cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.6"

AB-LHR-10-GS12 N Face
18cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS12 E Face
18cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS13 N Face
19cm across 16cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.6"

AB-LHR-10-GS13 E Face
19cm across 16cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.6"

AB-LHR-24-GS1 S Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.0"

AB-LHR-24-GS1 W Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.0"

AB-LHR-24-GS2 S Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS2 W Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS1 N Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.0"

AB-LHR-24-GS1 E Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.0"

AB-LHR-24-GS2 N Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS2 E Face
24cm across 24cm thick 110cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-10-GS1 NE Face
15cm across 11cm thick 46cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-10-GS1 SE Face
15cm across 11cm thick 46cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-10-GS10 S Face
15cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS10 W Face
15cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS1 SW Face
15cm across 11cm thick 46cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-10-GS1 NW Face
15cm across 11cm thick 46cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AAB-LHR-10-GS10 N Face
15cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-10-GS10 E Face
15cm across 15cm thick 49cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.7" E: 095 31' 47.7"

AB-LHR-30-GS3 S Face
16cm across 14cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 41.6" E: 095 31' 54.3"

AB-LHR-30-GS3 W Face
16cm across 14cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 41.6" E: 095 31' 54.3"

AB-LHR-10-GS6 S Face
20cm across 15cm thick 53cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-10-GS6 W Face
20cm across 15cm thick 53cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-30-GS3 N Face
16cm across 14cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 41.6" E: 095 31' 54.3"

AB-LHR-30-GS3 E Face
16cm across 14cm thick 78cm tall
N: 05 36' 41.6" E: 095 31' 54.3"

AB-LHR-10-GS6 N Face
20cm across 15cm thick 53cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-10-GS6 E Face
20cm across 15cm thick 53cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.6" E: 095 31' 47.8"

AB-LHR-24-GS3 SE Face
18cm across 18cm thick 86cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS3 SWFace
18cm across 18cm thick 86cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-33-GS3 W Face
20cm across 17cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.5" E: 095 32' 01.1"

AB-LHR-33-GS3 N Face
20cm across 17cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.5" E: 095 32' 01.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS3 NW Face
18cm across 18cm thick 86cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-24-GS3 NE Face
18cm across 18cm thick 86cm tall
N: 05 36' 44.1" E: 095 31' 51.1"

AB-LHR-33-GS3 E Face
20cm across 17cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.5" E: 095 32' 01.1"

AB-LHR-33-GS3 S Face
20cm across 17cm thick 70cm tall
N: 05 36' 39.5" E: 095 32' 01.1"

AB-LHR-50-GS1 S Face
27cm across 23cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 13.1" E: 095 32' 01.2"

AB-LHR-50-GS1 W Face
27cm across 23cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 13.1" E: 095 32' 01.2"

AB-LHR-39-GS6 S Face
18cm across 18cm thick 68cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.5" E: 095 31' 55.4"

AB-LHR-39-GS6 W Face
18cm across 18cm thick 68cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.5" E: 095 31' 55.4"

AB-LHR-50-GS1 N Face
27cm across 23cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 13.1" E: 095 32' 01.2"

AB-LHR-50-GS1 E Face
27cm across 23cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 13.1" E: 095 32' 01.2"

AB-LHR-39-GS6 N Face
18cm across 18cm thick 68cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.5" E: 095 31' 55.4"

AB-LHR-39-GS6 E Face
18cm across 18cm thick 68cm tall
N: 05 36' 36.5" E: 095 31' 55.4"

AB-LHR-46-GS4 SW Face
15cm across 15cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-46-GS4 NW Face
15cm across 15cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-43-GS1 SE Face
17cm across 13cm thick 58cm tall
N: 05 36' 32.35" E: 095 31' 57.83"

AB-LHR-43-GS1 SW Face
17cm across 13cm thick 58cm tall
N: 05 36' 32.35" E: 095 31' 57.83"

AB-LHR-46-GS4 NE Face
15cm across 15cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-46-GS4 SE Face
15cm across 15cm thick 63cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-43-GS1 NW Face
17cm across 13cm thick 58cm tall
N: 05 36' 32.35" E: 095 31' 57.83"

AB-LHR-43-GS1 NE Face
17cm across 13cm thick 58cm tall
N: 05 36' 32.35" E: 095 31' 57.83"

AB-LHR-60-GS4 S Face
18cm across 17cm thick 80cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.32" E: 095 32' 02.85"

AB-LHR-60-GS4 W Face
18cm across 17cm thick 80cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.32" E: 095 32' 02.85"

AB-LHR-46-GS5 SW Face
21cm across 16cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-46-GS5 NW Face
21cm across 16cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-60-GS4 N Face
18cm across 17cm thick 80cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.32" E: 095 32' 02.85"

AB-LHR-60-GS4 E Face
18cm across 17cm thick 80cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.32" E: 095 32' 02.85"

AB-LHR-46-GS5 NE Face
21cm across 16cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-46-GS5 SE Face
21cm across 16cm thick 87cm tall
N: 05 36' 35.4" E: 095 31' 55.5"

AB-LHR-58-GS1
23cm across 75cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 05.4"

AB-LHR-70-GS1
47cm across 23cm thick 90cm tall
N: 05 35' 27.8" E: 095 31' 40.7"

AB-LHR-70-GS4
30cm across 23cm thick 97cm tall
N: 05 35' 27.8" E: 095 31' 40.7"

AB-LHR-70-GS5
13cm across 8cm thick 37cm tall
N: 05 35' 28.0" E: 095 31' 40.7"

AB-LHR-58-GS2
23cm across 75cm tall
N: 05 36' 34.1" E: 095 32' 05.4"

AB-LHR-70-GS2
47cm across 23cm thick 90cm tall
N: 05 35' 27.9" E: 095 31' 40.6"

AB-LHR-70-GS3
32cm across 23cm thick 88cm tall
N: 05 35' 28.2" E: 095 31' 40.8"